

USE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGY IN THE TEACHING AND LEARNING OF SAFETY MINDSET AND PROCESS OPERATION SKILLS

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Abstract

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) implemented a suite of 4 skills-based module in its spiral curriculum to progressively develop in students a safety mindset alongside the technical competencies required by process technicians in the chemical processing industries as specified in the Singapore Skills Framework. The work reported in this paper focusses on the training of students to prepare equipment for maintenance (mechanical work) in a module *Process Operation Skills 1 (POS1)*. Preparation of equipment to render it safe for maintenance requires students to apply Workplace Safety and Health (WSH) through identification of hazards and the control measures to take, and application of the Safe System of Work (SSoW) framework and Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) according to the process where the equipment is used. Due to the students' lack of real-world working experience and the absence of prior experience on mechanical work, learning of WSH and SSoW in this context was done by referencing prior knowledge of WSH learnt previously then scaffolded gradually across several learning activities in *POS1*. Research has shown that immersive digital technology benefits student learning through its degree of realism that allows easy transfer of learnt skills and knowledge to real life and its student-centricness that allows self-paced learning, and repeated practice for tasks. Therefore, an Immersive Virtual Experiment (IVE) made in-house to isolate a control valve was used to develop competency in preparing an equipment for maintenance. Students will then demonstrate competency by transferring this learning to the preparation of a process equipment by isolating a pump in a pump circuit on a physical test skid in the workshop. Survey findings showed that the IVE was effective as students were more engaged and could better visualise and understand the rationale behind the steps to isolate a control valve. Most agreed or strongly agreed that they felt more prepared to demonstrate knowledge transfer to isolating and preparing a pump (equipment) for maintenance in a physical setup. Finally, plans to continue development of the safety mindset and other technical competences for process

technicians using digital technology in the DCHE curriculum are shared.

Keywords: *Safety Mindset, CDIO, Process Technicians, Chemical Engineering*

Introduction

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) from Singapore Polytechnic (SP) trains its students to work as process technicians in the chemical processing industries (CPI). Having a safety mindset is of utmost importance in the CPI, as they typically handle hazardous materials that are toxic and flammable, and these materials are used in processes that operates at high temperatures and pressures. Exercising extreme caution is also required when shutting down a processing plant for example for maintenance or debottlenecking. The same is true when starting up a processing plant from ambient condition. This paper is concerned with training students to prepare equipment for maintenance (mechanical work) when necessary, or after a shutdown.

Developing Safety Mindset using CDIO Framework

Based on the hierarchy of Info-Communication Technologies (ICT) utilisation suggested by Anderson (2010), this paper adapted the work of Yang & Cheah (2020) to show how safety mindset can be progressively developed using the CDIO Framework (www.cdio.org).

Figure 1. Progressive development of safety mindset using Digital Technologies

CDIO is an innovative framework for redesigning engineering curriculum that had been used by DCHE since 2007. The CDIO Framework comprises the CDIO

Syllabus and a set of 12 CDIO Standards. The CDIO Syllabus guides the writing of learning outcomes while the CDIO Standards guides the curriculum redesign process.

With regards to development of safety mindset (CDIO Standard 2 *Learning Outcomes*) in the CPI, we took reference from the Singapore Skills Framework (SSF) for the Energy & Chemicals (E&C) Sector, which covers the CPI (SSG, 2017). Specifically, the Job Role Description for Process Technician mandates that process technicians attained Proficiency Level 2 in the context of this work, in the following technical competencies:

- Workplace Safety and Health (WSH) Development and Implementation
- Workplace Safety and Health (WSH) Hazard Identification and Risk Control Management
- Safe System of Work (SSoW) Development and Implementation
- Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) Development and Implementation
- Process Operations Troubleshooting
- Process Equipment Preparation for Mechanical Work

According to the SSF, Level 2 proficiency requires the following attainment as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Proficiency Level 2 for Process Technician

Responsibility (Degree of supervision and accountability)	Work with some supervision Accountable for a broader set of tasks assigned
Autonomy (Degree of decision-making)	Use limited discretion in resolving issues or enquiries. Work without frequently looking to other for guidance
Complexity (Degree of difficulty of situations and tasks)	Routine
Knowledge and Abilities (Required to support work as described under Responsibility, Autonomy and Complexity)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand and apply factual and procedural knowledge in a field of work • Apply basic cognitive and technical skills to carry out defined tasks and to solve routine problems using simple procedures and tools • Present ideas and improve work

For Process Technician, the generic competencies are: Teamwork, Interpersonal Skills, Communication, Digital Literacy and Problem Solving, all pegged at Basic Level, as defined in Table 2.

Safety mindset in DCHE students is to be developed via the program’s spiral curriculum shown in Figure 2, which was designed using CDIO principles, namely Standard 3 *Integrated Curriculum* (Cheah & Yang, 2018). More specifically, this is to be achieved via 4 skills-based modules over 2 years that provides the best context for learning about the job role and responsibilities of Process Technicians (CDIO Standard 1 *The Context*): *Laboratory & Process Skills 1 (LPS1)* and *Laboratory & Process Skills 2 (LPS2)* in Year 1, and *Process Operations Skills*

1 (POS1) and *Process Operations Skills 2 (POS2)* in Year 2. The work reported in this paper was carried out in *POS1*, taken by DCHE students in Year 2, Semester 1.

Table 2. Basic Level Proficiency for Process Technician

Competency	Requirement for Basic Level
Teamwork	Contribute to a positive and cooperative working environment by fulfilling own responsibilities and providing support to coworkers to achieve team goals.
Interpersonal Skills	Recognise own internal feelings and emotional states to manage inter-personal relationships in social situations.
Communication	Communicate information with others to respond to general inquiries and to obtain specific information.
Digital Literacy	Perform basic functions using software programmes pertaining to computer operating systems and file management, and search online information.
Problem Solving	Identify easily perceivable problems and follow given guidelines and procedures to solve the problems.

Figure 2. The DCHE Spiral Curriculum

The work done in *POS1* is a continuation of earlier effort to instil safety mindset in DCHE students, starting in *LPS1* where general workplace safety awareness is cultivated using Virtual Reality training (Yang & Cheah, 2020), and laboratory safety was taught using *Job Safety Analysis*. Then in *LPS2*, students were exposed to *Process Hazard Analysis* when operating simple pilot plants. Such training comprises a blend of physical plants as well as virtual ones (Cheah, 2022; Cheah, 2021), designed based on CDIO Standard 7 *Integrated Learning Experiences*, where technical knowledge, skills and attitudes are all developed simultaneously using scenarios that mimic real-world work environment. Constructive alignment was used to check for attainment of learning outcomes using both formative and summative assessments (CDIO Standard 11 *Learning Assessment*).

Integrated Learning Experiences in POSI

This module has 9 learning activities, designed to provide students with a range of simulated real-world working environment of what process technicians do in their stipulated job role. Selected learning activities aimed at progressively developing students' abovementioned key competencies for Process Technicians as stipulated in the SSF for E&C Sector are shown in Table 3. The work reported in this paper is carried out in Week 4, which is intended to support the later activity of preparing an equipment for maintenance in Week 6.

Since our students do not have any real-world experience working in the CPI, we have to slowly scaffold the learning activities to implement WSH and SSoW plans. We leveraged on their prior knowledge in LPS2 in the previous semester on WSH awareness and Process Hazard Analysis to progressively engaging them in activities with increasing complexity in POSI. We therefore decided to use isolation of a control valve and flushing of its associated piping as the basis to develop competency in preparing an equipment for maintenance. The choice of control valve is a good fit as it is commonly found in the CPI, and our students had experience operating it in LPS2.

Table 3. Selected Learning Activities in POSI

Week	Learning Activities	Competency
1	Workplace Safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reinforce and extend competency covered in LPS2
2	P&ID Reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reinforce competency covered in LPS2
3	Preparing SOP for inter-tank transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WSH implementation: Hazard Identification and Control Management SSoW & SOP development for tank transfer operation
4	Isolation of a control valve and flushing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WSH implementation: Hazard Identification and Control Management SSoW & SOP implementation for control valve isolation
5	Performing inter-tank transfer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WSH implementation: Hazard Identification and Control Management SSoW & SOP implementation for tank transfer operation
6	Isolation of a pump in a pump circuit and flushing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WSH implementation: Hazard Identification and Control Management SSoW & SOP implementation for pump isolation Process Equipment Preparation for Mechanical Work

Students will then need to demonstrate their ability to transfer the learning from control valve isolation to the preparation of a process equipment – isolating a pump and its associated components (filter, check valve and pipes) in this case – for flushing to remove any remnant chemicals in the pipes. This activity will be carried on Week 6, using a physical test skid in our workshop (see

Figure 3). Students will submit a group report on their work done and a reflection journal of their learning experiences of the activities in Weeks 4 and 6.

Figure 3. Test Skid for Preparing Equipment for Maintenance

We opted to use an Immersive Virtual Experiment (IVE) for this training, taking into considerations our large student cohort size (100-120 students per semester), that made it impractical to have many pilot plants in limited workshop space. The other consideration is that our students do not have any prior experience in carrying out mechanical work.

IVE for Control Valve Isolation

Immersive virtual experiment (IVE) is a digital learning package prepared in-house by SP. It is akin to a digital twin in that it a computer model based on real physical item; and offers interaction between students and a section of the processing plant of interest. It lacked the dynamic modelling of digital twin and uses simple animations to reflect the interactions with the item to engage users in learning the content. Through animations various hazardous scenarios can be created when students did not follow the SOP, or did not undertake proper safe work practices. The IVE offered the following advantages in student learning:

- Residing in every student's laptop, the IVE allows each student the freedom to practice as often as he/she wanted, and one's own convenience (place and time).
- Learning from mistakes: students can better appreciate the consequence(s) of not adhering to SOPs or overlooked a hazard during the risk assessment process in a safe environment.

The IVE is modelled after a section of the actual test skid that students will work on in Week 6. Figure 4 showed a schematic diagram (known as the piping and instrumentation diagram or P&ID) for a typical control valve station. Students had already learnt how to read P&IDs by interpreting the symbols used; and conduct line tracing in LPS2.

Figure 5 showed the IVE for control valve station produced by SP's in-house technical support team, with 2 of the authors serving as subject matter experts.

The prototype IVE was tested with 8 student volunteers from an earlier cohort who had completed POSI, and their input helped to refine the software

package. The IVE was subsequently rolled out in Semester 1 Academic Year 2023/2024.

Figure 4. Schematic Diagram of developing the IVE

Figure 5. Virtual Control Valve in the IVE

The following are some of the tasks in the IVE that students are required to complete in order to demonstrate attainment of the desired learning outcomes (CDIO Standard 11 *Learning Assessment*):

- WSH Development and Implementation, Hazard Identification and Risk Control Management:
 1. Identify proper safety permits to use
 2. Proper barricade work area for restricted access
 3. Appropriate signage to warn of hazards present
 4. Select appropriate tools for the task on hand
- Process Equipment Preparation for Mechanical Work:
 1. Arrange in correct sequence the given SOP
 2. Identify suitable location to break flange
 3. **Coordination with Boardman in Control Room**
 4. Provision of secondary containment to reduce contamination of environment by residual liquid in the control valve and its piping

Evaluation of Students' Learning Experience

A mixed-method survey was designed to evaluate the students' learning experience using the IVE in Week 4, and its effectiveness in helping them prepare for the activity in Week 6.

A 5-point Likert-Scale was used where students were required to rate from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree" on the following five questions:

1. The amount of content covered in the IVE was just nice.
2. I felt engaged (committed and motivated) when going through the IVE.
3. The simulations in the IVE has enabled me to better visualise the task at hand.
4. The knowledge checks in the IVE helped to check my understanding.
5. After doing the IVE, I feel more prepared to perform the practical on maintenance work in W319.

Students were then asked to estimate the amount of time they spent on the IVE, and finally to answer the following two open-ended questions:

6. Based on your response to Question 5, elaborate on your choice.
7. Suggest other ways(s) in which the IVE can help you be more prepared to perform the practical on maintenance work in W319.

The survey was administered to all six classes of students reading *POSI*, and 88 students voluntary completed the survey.

Discussion

87.5% of the students surveyed found the IVE content coverage sufficient for their learning of control valve isolation, hazard identification and implementation of WSH and *SoW* (Figure 6), with most completing it in 30 minutes or less (92.0%; Figure 7), and this timeframe allowed them to remain engaged throughout its use (87.5%; Figure 6). These findings were similar to that reported by others (Huang et al, 2016; Colombo & Golzio, 2016; Huang et al, 2010) where learning experiences and student engagement were enhanced by the use of immersive technology.

Figure 6. Content Coverage of IVE and Student Engagement when using IVE

Figure 7. Time Spent on IVE

87.5% of students strongly agree or agree that the IVE was effective in preparing them to transfer what they learnt from the IVE and demonstrate it in another context - the activity carried out in Week 6 where they had to prepare a process equipment (a pump) in the workshop (W319) for maintenance (Figure 8). This was attributed to the interactivity and clarity of each step in the IVE as shared by one student:

“The IVE made it clear on what key tasks were involved in the maintenance work and how to perform the tasks“

A student opined that the IVE

“allowed me to know the different permits needed”

which is a key requirement when preparing equipment for maintenance based on the SSoW framework.

Nonetheless, there were a still few students who had some reservations (2.3% disagree or strongly disagree; Figure 8) on their degree of preparedness to demonstrate transfer and application of knowledge. This lack of confidence was not surprising as this was the first instance students had to perform mechanical work during their diploma studies. One student shared:

“I felt mostly prepared to perform isolation, but not fully since there are differences in doing isolation for a control valve and a pump.”

Figure 8. Effectiveness of IVE for Learning

The overall positive sentiments on the effectiveness of IVE for learning, and the engagement that students felt when using the IVE can be attributed to three factors: the knowledge checks, the interactivity and the realistic visuals/ animations. 92.0% of students strongly agreed or agreed that the knowledge checks provided insights to how well they understood the content in the IVE, and the specific section(s) that they may need to re-visit (Figure 8) to meet the learning outcomes in the IVE. Through the interactivity and realism provided in the IVE, students were able to better visualise the planning and execution processes needed to prepare an equipment for maintenance and developing simultaneously the safety mindset needed (89.8% strongly agree or agree; Figure 8) even though they had no prior experience in carrying out such mechanical work. They were able to identify the hazards and measures needed to mitigate or control these hazards. This was followed by identifying the permits needed in the SSoW, and finally sequencing the steps that will lead to the isolation of the control valve (SOP). Consequences were also shown if the SOP was not followed. These were succinctly articulated by two students

“The IVE gave me a better idea on how to perform practical 6 as it is visually enriching, and it helped to guide me through the different steps that needed to be taken during the isolation and preparation of the equipment for maintenance.”

“It helped me to visualise what I have to do with my team for maintenance work. For example, which isolation valves to close first.”

Similar sentiments were also articulated in the students’ reflection journals that were submitted after the learning activities in Weeks 4 and 6, as shown in snippets of entries from two students’ reflections:

“Through P5 and P6, I learnt that the planning stage is crucial in the context of preparing equipment or a system for shutdown for several reasons. Firstly, the biggest point of concern during any plant activity: safety. Proper planning allows for a comprehensive assessment of potential risks, identification of safety procedures, and implementation of necessary precautions. This includes ensuring that appropriate isolation procedures are followed, hazardous materials are handled safely, and potential safety hazards are mitigated.”

“Preparing SOP helps me to visualise what I would be doing during the practical, which helps me to conduct a risk assessment. This ensures that the potential hazards are acknowledged and there would be lower risks of the incidents happening. These skills help me become a safe and professional operations technician in the future.”

These positive survey findings show that the IVE was useful to develop in students the desired safety mindset alongside the key competencies required by Process Technicians as stipulated in the SSF for E&C sector (Table 3), similar to that reported by Colombo & Golzio (2016) who found that immersive technology when used for training in the process industry enabled more learning compared to traditional didactic training.

Conclusion

The experience of using an immersive virtual experiment (IVE) to train students to prepare equipment for maintenance with a safety mindset, which are key competencies for Process Technicians in the E&C Sector was shared here. Survey findings from the students' experiences in using the IVE to learn WSH, and SSoW and SOP implementation for control valve isolation, and subsequently to transfer this learning to that of pump isolation and maintenance was positive. The benefits of the IVE in teaching and learning of these skills can be clearly summarised by one student's sharing

"It helped visualise an otherwise difficult area of study to imagine without seeing firsthand examples and thus assisted in understanding of the process as well as the tasks we are supposed to do"

This is very encouraging, given that the realism of the visuals and interactivity to actual operations in immersive digital technology (Nazir & Manca, 2015) make such technology a natural fit for teaching and learning of knowledge and skills for industries such as chemical process when there is a need to transfer the acquired knowledge or skills readily to actual equipment or processes or to replicate conditions for training that would otherwise be unsafe or impossible to carry out in real life (Norton et al, 2008; Fracaro et al, 2022, Koskela et al, 2005; Addison et al, 2013, and Liu et al, 2010).

Consequently, DCHE is reviewing and purposefully designing more activities with greater complexity that leverage on similar technology to further develop safety mindset and key competencies to the desired proficiency level as required by process technicians in the E&C sector. One activity would be the use of digital twin of an actual pilot plant to let students operate a pilot plant under different scenarios such as a sudden plant upset, and learn how to respond in these situations while maintaining safety.

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